

1. Additional RADMC3D Models

1.1. Setup and model parameters

We set up a 3D grid comprising $250 \times 250 \times 250$ points and constructed a simple spherical distribution with a single star at the centre of the grid. The temperature was set to 3500 K, which is also derived from the observed spectra of V838 Mon. The size of the star was set to $1420 R_{\odot}$ and the dust distribution was restricted to a box with dimensions $100 \times 100 \times 100$ au. For all our simulations, we used an amorphous dust grain mixture comprising amorphous pyroxene with 70% Mg-rich and 30% Fe-rich. The density was set to $2 \times 10^{-17} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The resulting dust mass we got from each simulation was $\sim 10^{-6} M_{\odot}$. In each simulation, we modified the simple spherical dust distribution in order to produce more complex dust morphologies.

With a custom python script along with the RADMC3D python wrapper `radmc3dPy`¹, we performed radiative transfer calculations for all of our simulated density distributions. Multiple scripts were created for each particular density distribution. By putting constraints on the positions and morphology of the dust grains in the scripts, we were able to create various dust geometries. These include jets, disks, blobs and their various combinations.

1.2. RADMC3D Models for V838 Mon

In every model except the Disk+Blobs model, the central star was shrouded by a spherical shell of dust that spanned 5 au. In the Disk+Blobs model, we have modified the central dust to resemble an elongated elliptical disk instead. The variations in the models were due to the different morphologies and components that we experimented with in the space surrounding the above described central dusty shell. The models and their particulars are described below.

1.2.1. Three Blobs

In this model, we utilize three spherical dust components that we call blobs. The blobs are generally oriented along the observed position angle of the infrared structure in the post merger remnant. The size of these blobs is 3 au, two of them are positioned diagonally from across each other, while the third blob is slightly offset with respect to the Northern one. This was done to make the dust distribution asymmetric, which is hinted at by the non-zero closure phase deviations which we see in the *HK* band observations. The resulting distributions of emission in the *K* and *H* bands, respectively, can be seen in Figs. 1 and 6.

1.2.2. Two Blobs

This model consists of two blobs that are aligned diagonally with respect to each other. The size of both the blobs is 3 au. In this model, the Northern blob has been made twice as dense as the central dust shell. Figs. 2 and 7 display these synthetic images.

1.2.3. North Jet Dense

In this model, the central dust shell is surrounded by bipolar conical features that extend in the South-East to North-West direction (see Figs.3 and 9). Jets are thought to be present in the cir-

cumstellar environment in V838 Mon. The density of the northern jet was set to twice that of the central dust shell. Furthermore, we also tested directionality, i.e. looking at the effect of making the Southern jet denser. We found that the resulting observables in both cases were indistinguishable, which is why we have presented only the singular case where the Northern jet is denser.

1.2.4. Jets+Blobs

This model consists of three distinct components exterior to the central dust shell (see Figs. 3 and 9). The Southern component is a jet feature, similar to what we have in the jets model. In the North we have added an elongated elliptical disk like feature, and in addition to this the model also contains a single blob in the North West. This model is the most complex in terms of its constituents. We constructed such a model for the purpose of testing the effect of increasing complexity on the interferometric observables.

1.2.5. Disk+Blobs

This model consists of a disk that is oriented along the position angle observed in V838 Mon with the above described blobs model (see Figs.5 and 10). This model is almost similar to the Two blobs model except in the fact that the central component instead of being a spherical shell is now an elliptical tilted disk.

¹ https://www.ita.uni-heidelberg.de/~dullemond/software/radmc-3d/manual_rmcpy/radmc3dPy.html

Fig. 1. *K* band image for Three Blobs model. The flux scale is logarithmic and the units are arbitrary.

Fig. 6. *H* band image for the Three Blobs model.

Fig. 2. *K* band image for Two Blobs model.

Fig. 7. *H* band image for the Two Blobs model.

Fig. 3. *K* band image for the North Jet Dense model.

Fig. 8. *H* band image for the North Jet Dense model.

Fig. 4. *K* band image for the Jets+Blobs model.

Fig. 9. *H* band image for the Jets+Blobs model.

Fig. 5. *K* band image for the Disk+Blobs model.

Fig. 10. *H* band image for the Disk+Blobs model.

Fig. 11. *K* band Three Blobs model squared visibilities simulated for VLT-GRAVITY.

Fig. 13. *K* band Northern Jet model squared visibilities.

Fig. 12. *K* band Two Blobs model squared visibilities.

Fig. 14. *K* band Jets+Blobs model squared visibilities.

2. *K* band model squared visibilities

Fig. 15. *K* band Disk+Blobs model squared visibilities.

Fig. 16. *K* band Three Blobs closure phases simulated for VLTI-GRAVITY.

Fig. 18. *K* band Northern Jet model closure phases.

Fig. 17. *K* band Two Blobs model closure phases.

Fig. 19. *K* band Jets+Blobs model closure phases.

3. *K* band model closure phases

Fig. 20. *K* band Disk+Blobs model closure phases.

Fig. 21. *H* band Three Blobs model squared visibilities.

Fig. 23. *H* band Northern Jet model squared visibilities.

Fig. 22. *H* band Two Blobs model squared visibilities.

Fig. 24. *H* band Jets+Blobs model squared visibilities.

4. *H* band model squared visibilities

Fig. 25. *H* band Disk+Blobs model squared visibilities.

Fig. 26. *H* band Three Blobs closure phases.

Fig. 28. *H* band Northern Jet model closure phases.

Fig. 27. *H* band Two Blobs model closure phases.

Fig. 29. *H* band Jets+Blobs model closure phases.

5. *H* band model closure phases

Fig. 30. *H* band Disk+Blobs model closure phases.